

RDA TIGER D1.2: Data Management Plan (version 3.0)

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	RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)
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3.0	28.02.2026	Alex Delipalta (RDA AISBL), Ryan O'Connor (RDA AISBL)	Final DMP at project end

Disclaimer

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

DMP	Data Management Plan
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable
OSS	Outputs Support Services
RDA	Research Data Alliance
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This is the final update to the DMP for the RDA TIGER project, written after the project concluded. The plans to manage data are represented in version 2; there were no significant changes to plans for managing data between versions 2.0 and 3.0. The plans put in place and described in version 2.0 were effective and resulted in correct handling of data according to the FAIR principles. The overall structure of this report reflects version 2.0; updates were made to refer to the latest reports and deliverables where related to processes for data management.

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1. Data Summary

The project collected the following kinds of data (the work package (WP) most concerned with the data type are noted in parentheses).

- I. **Internal project documents (all WPs).** These documents contained working documents on service descriptions, milestones, deliverables and other similar internal documents as well as documentation related to human resources (staff contracts, contracts with in-house consultants, contracts with external experts performing subcontracting, timesheets, etc.). These are created in the project lifetime by project partners, and are usually normal office documents (text documents, spreadsheets, etc.) of small size. These data have limited interest outside of the consortium. The data need to be retained in line with Horizon Europe retention requirements (5 years record keeping requirement for RDA TIGER as per GA).
- II. **External project documentation (Deliverables, other reports, dissemination material) (all WPs).** These documents are official outputs of the project, including service descriptions, quality indicators, and service processes, as well as project publications and dissemination materials. These documents are all public and intended for discovery and reuse. They will be deposited in a trustworthy repository (Zenodo) and licensed with an open licence that permits reuse (CC-BY). The volume of these data is limited (below 1Gb), and they are typically PDF documents. The data will be utilised by RDA in the future, as well as other organisations wanting to create similar services for supporting group work globally.
- III. **Contact lists (WP1, WP2, WP5, WP6).** RDA TIGER activities necessitated the compilation of a number of contact lists. These included consortium-internal mailing list of project partners (WP1), list of potential external experts to propose to TIGER-supported WGs (WP1), event registration and attendee lists (WP2), stakeholder lists of TIGER-supported WGs (WP2, WP3, WP5), as well as list of Selection Committee members (WP6). These contact lists included personal contact information of RDA TIGER stakeholders, project personnel and involved parties; the contact information was either directly volunteered by RDA TIGER stakeholders when they attend RDA TIGER related events or acquired via searchers of publicly accessible websites (e.g. stakeholders' institutional websites). These data are in different structured formats (e.g., spreadsheets), and of small size. These data are not intended for reuse after the end of the project; the existing data files are destroyed at the end of the project. RDA TIGER supported WGs receive support via the Facilitation Service to involve stakeholders directly via the RDA web platform to ensure that they retain access to stakeholders after the end of the project.

In detail, the data lifecycle for stakeholder lists of TIGER-supported WGs (WP2, WP3, WP5) is the following. At the outset of each supported WG, the RDA TIGER facilitator worked with WG co-chairs to draw up an initial list of contacts (individuals and organisations) to invite to join the WG. It varied from WG to WG, but these lists typically contained names, email addresses and regions, in addition to organisational information such as whether the contact has responded or have indicated they will join the WG. Access to these lists is limited to RDA TIGER project partners and the WG co-chairs, and were stored on the internal RDA project Google Drive. Once the WG was endorsed, communication with WG members took place using the RDA website functions; these lists were then archived, with the intention to permanently delete these at the end of the project (regardless of whether the WG has completed its activities).

- IV. **Data and documents regarding applications (WP1, WP6).** Applications for TIGER support, both ongoing Open Calls as well as Cascade Grant applications, collected some personal data about applicants (name, affiliation, country, email, history of involvement with RDA) as well as data about the applicants' proposed project and/or the activities of a RDA working group for which support is sought. Applicants fill in a MS Office form (data collected include applicant's name, email address, and RDA group affiliation and these data are stored in SharePoint). Upon completion of the MS Office form, applicants received instructions for uploading their full applications to B2DROP, which allowed access-control application management in the review stage (see section 2.5 below); after review was complete, applications were stored in SharePoint. These data are retained in SharePoint for the duration of GA mandated retention period (5 years), after which time they are destroyed.

Following the B2DROP service disruption, all application processes previously carried out via B2DROP were transferred to Sharepoint, using Sharepoint Forms.

- V. **Open science landscape data (WP3, WP4).** These data comprised information (metadata) on open science initiatives, RDA groups, outputs, and similar complex objects, and connections between them. The data were collected in structured formats (spreadsheets) and transformed into project deliverables (data type II) and also a more organised graph database (data type VIII). The data contained information on projects, initiatives, and outputs, as well as internet links. The data were intended to be re-usable after the project via the RDA Knowledge Base (formerly referred to as the Maintenance Platform). Deliverable 3.6¹ and associated visualisations are available through kumu.io²
- VI. **Service quality indicators and feedback (WP6).** The service feedback data were collected from targets, providers, customers, and beneficiaries of the RDA TIGER services. These are collected in two ways; via a Google Form or via a dedicated email address (rdatiger-feedback@rd-alliance.org). Responses to the Google Form can sometimes contain personal information in the open-ended questions; the respondents also have the option to add their name and contact address to their responses. Feedback received via the dedicated email address are stored together with the feedback data received via Google Forms. Some of the quality indicator information were restructured for anonymity or analysis. The indicators were both numeric and qualitative, usually stored in spreadsheets and text documents. The quality information were intended to be re-used in abridged form during the lifetime of the RDA TIGER project to improve the service usability; anonymised quality information are also integrated in project deliverables (data type II); all identifiable service quality feedback was destroyed at the end of the project.
- VII. **Working Group documents and outputs (WP5).** The RDA TIGER project supports its WGs to develop clear processes to document the WG's activity and progress. As part of this, RDA TIGER provided WG co-chairs with template documents for setting up meeting agendas and note-taking. These were typically set up on the RDA TIGER project's Google Drive and accessible by WG co-chairs and members. They contained names of WG members (usually in the form of meeting 'attendance sheets'). Once a WG completed its activities, these documents were archived, then deleted once the RDA TIGER project ended. In cases where the WG activities are ongoing at the time the RDA TIGER project ends, the ownership of

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/17877370>

² <https://kumu.io/>

collaborative documents related to WG activity was passed on to WG co-chairs who will continue to work with these documents in line with the RDA Code of Conduct.³

WGs also produced stand-alone outputs in the form of RDA endorsed Recommendations and Supporting Outputs; the initial and final versions of these were published openly, with the RDA community invited to provide feedback. The ownership of these is with the WG co-chairs and RDA in general; they do not fall under the purview of the RDA TIGER data management plan.

Any documentation maintained on the RDA TIGER (hosted by the RDA AISBL) Google Drive was transferred to designated WG co-chairs in December 2025.

VIII. **RDA Graph (WP2, WP4, WP5).** The RDA TIGER WP4 Outputs Support Services (OSS) aimed to ensure quality, usefulness, and sustainability of the WG outputs. This involved the creation and maintenance of a graph-relational database of RDA-related resources. Such resources included publicly available RDA WG outputs, publicly available information about RDA WG co-chairs and members (thereby overlapping somewhat with V and VII above), as well as publicly available bibliographical information about authors, affiliations, institutions, licenses, and any relations between resources. In addition, the RDA Annotator creates annotations for any web-based information, together with associated vocabularies. Further details regarding the RDA Graph and RDA Annotator and the types of data it stores can be found in [D4.2 – Description of Output Support Services and Maintenance Platform, Annex D.](#)⁴ The RDA Graph Database – which is the maintenance facility developed by RDA TIGER – is accessible and reusable after the end of the project. RDA KB documentation is available on Zenodo^{5 6}.

2. FAIR DATA

The data created in the RDA TIGER were stored and managed in different data service platforms. The table below summarises storage and management approaches per data type.

*Table 1 Data management solutions used in the RDA TIGER per data type. "Working" refers to document location during the project-time activities (e.g., drafts, online shared documents being edited, etc.), and "long term" refers to a solution intended for long time data management (including after-project storage). Terms in parenthesis indicate secondary or temporary use. *) only for successful applications and their relevant associated information, **) only connectivity (i.e., metadata and linkages) are stored in this facility, not the actual data.*

Data no	Type	Google folders	RDA Website	Commission	Zenodo	B2DROP	Sharepoint	Knowledge Base
I	Internal documents	Working					Working, Long term	

³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/code-of-conduct/>

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12568753>

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18739795>

⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17737223>

II	External documents	Working	Long term	Long term	Long term	Long term **
III	Contact lists	Working				Working
IV	Applications				Working	Working, Long-term
V	Landscape data	Working				Working, long term
VI	Quality data	Working				Working
VII	WG data	Working	Working, long term		Long term	Long term **
VIII	RDA Graph Database	Working				Long term

Below, we discuss the different data management tools used, and adhere to the FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability) principles.

2.1 Google folder tree

Corresponding data types: I, II, III, V, VI, VII

Google-operated office suite (drive.google.com) and shared documents. For the documents and information needed for mostly internal purposes, the main findability issue is to make sure they are shareable and secure in the internal storage systems of the project. A shared Google folder system was used, where the documents are arranged according to the WP. Access to the folder system was limited on a need to access basis either to (i) RDA TIGER project staff, (ii) RDA TIGER project staff + WG co-chairs (WG-specific sub folders under WP5 folder), or (iii) anyone with the link (WG membership working sub-folders under WP5 folder). This folder tree was maintained by WP1. Some personal data was stored in Google folders; this concerned data type III, i.e. contact lists, which included data directly offered by data subjects or available via publicly accessible websites (i.e. stakeholders’ institutional websites). No human resources and contracts related data (data type I) was stored in the Google folder system.

FAIR implications: Findability via folder structure by project consortium members only. Accessibility: The Google folder structure was mostly intended for project internal use and access was limited to project staff; some sub-folders of WP5 were accessible via direct links also to RDA TIGER supported WG co-chairs and/or RDA TIGER supported WG co-chairs and members. Interoperability: Limited internal metadata included in most documents for internal use, use of standard templates for critical information. Necessary metadata for internal use was included in the files as much as is reasonable. Re-usability: Most data in the Google storage system was not intended for re-use after the project; RDA TIGER supported WGs data in the WG-specific subfolders under WP5 passed ownership to relevant WG co-chairs after the end of the project.

2.2. RDA website

Corresponding data types: II, VII

Website platform (rd-alliance.org), with a rich document repository and wide range of information, particularly for the Working Group documents. The platform was updated (partly via contribution via RDA TIGER service purchase) and acted as the main virtual collaboration platform for WG work (type VII). The document platform also included additional documentation of RDA (type II) and was commonly seen as the primary platform for the community to search for RDA documents. The platform has long term sustainability, and it has a regular back-up schedule.

FAIR implications: Findability via tagging and persistent (i.e. non-changing in technology migration) URLs (also linked in many DOIs). Accessibility: Generally open access, some documents (mostly working documents) only for the WG members. Interoperability: Limited internal metadata included in most documents, use of standard templates for critical information. Necessary metadata for internal use was included in the files as much as is reasonable. Re-usability: Document platform is available for re-use, although lack of specific metadata or documentation can limit the usability of some outputs. This is considered in RDA TIGER WP4 actions for output documentation.

2.3. Commission services

Corresponding data types: II

The European Commission operates their own document repository for project outputs, particularly for the project deliverables. In practice, all RDA TIGER deliverables which are public are de-facto published in the CORDIS database (cordis.europa.eu) for public use, and the European Commission platform acts as a permanent repository for these documents.

FAIR implications: Findability via tagging and permanent URLs, although by experience a small number of direct searchers are done in these services. Accessibility: Openly accessible with no registration via the CORDIS database. Interoperability: Limited internal metadata included in most documents, use of standard templates for critical information. Necessary metadata for internal use is included in the files as much as is reasonable. Re-usability: Depending on the document.

2.4. Zenodo

Corresponding data types: II, VII

Zenodo repository platform (zenodo.org) offers a long-term trustworthy repository environment for documents and data. Operated by CERN, it has a service promise for sustained long term stability. All RDA TIGER public documents (data type II) are deposited in Zenodo, and included in the RDA TIGER Zenodo Community created for the project. Standard Zenodo metadata, which follows DataCite metadata schema essential elements, is included for all outputs uploaded by the RDA TIGER. While

Zenodo permits restricted access deposits, all RDA TIGER outputs deposited in Zenodo are deposited as open access resources with appropriate open licenses (CC-BY).

FAIR implications: Findability via standardised metadata, DOIs and multiple services harvesting the Zenodo APIs. Accessibility: Openly accessible with no registration. Interoperability: Limited internal metadata included in most documents, use of standard templates for critical information. Necessary metadata for internal use is included in the files as much as is reasonable. Re-usability: Open licensing (CC-BY) and use of standardised templates supports re-use.

2.5. B2DROP

Corresponding data types: IV

B2DROP was used initially; due to a service interruption files stored there were lost. However, the project management team had made backups of the majority of the affected documentation, and others were still available through the email application submission process. Files were subsequently securely stored on Sharepoint.

2.6. SHAREPOINT

Corresponding data types: I, III, IV, VI

Professional virtual platform of the RDA Association (operated by RDA Foundation) and provided by the Microsoft services. Access to this platform is more secured and limited than for the Google services (2.1. above). The platform has the benefit of business-level backup services (paid by RDA Association contract) and authenticated access. This service is used in RDA TIGER for long term storage of those project records that fall under GA-mandated 5-year record-keeping requirement but cannot be deposited in open repositories like Zenodo (data types I, III, IV) as well as for the storing of data that contains sensitive or identifiable information, e.g. raw service feedback data and contact lists which need to be secured due to GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) concerns (data types I, III, VI).

FAIR implications: Findability via internal folder system and document naming. Accessibility: Only for strictly specified personnel with appropriate rda-foundation.org authentication (Microsoft Authenticator is active). Interoperability: Applications have internal metadata. Re-usability: only internal use.

2.7. RDA Knowledge Base

Corresponding data types: II, V, VII, VIII

The RDA Knowledge Base⁷ (RDA-KB; formerly referred as the Knowledge Base) intended to ensure the quality, usefulness, and sustainability of WG outputs, and consists of a suite of tools for the

⁷ <https://www.kb-rda.org/>

publication, annotation, discovery, and preservation of such resources. The RDA-KB stores metadata associated with the data types described above, and has the ability to prepare such metadata for deposit with long-term repositories such as Zenodo. This service is described in more detail in the deliverable D4.2⁸ and D4.3⁹. All

FAIR implications: The RDA-KB, particularly as it is connected to the RDA (upgraded) website, will provide additional findability of the digital records involved in the facility. The Knowledge Base provides additional accessibility and interoperability due to additional metadata involved in the documented data systems. Reusability will be significantly improved due to tagging with topic-related keywords of interest to the community.

3. Allocation of resources

The project involved internal resources for data management, particularly in the WP1, WP4, and WP6. The resources included personnel resources for the management activities, as well as development of Knowledge Base connectivity in WP4. Additionally, the project included resources for concrete management actions:

- Partial funding of RDA Website development task to make sure the website is usable for the RDA TIGER support services. This contribution is marked as direct purchase of goods and is handled via contract with RDA Foundation.
- WP1 included direct costs to pay for partial use (for RDA Association personnel) of the SharePoint service platform.

The usage of Zenodo, B2DROP and Commission services are currently free at the point-of-use.

4. Data security

The data produced in the RDA TIGER project had modest data security needs. Human resources and contracts data (data type I) was accessible for defined, authenticated project staff only (project coordinator, coordinator financial officer, HR, auditors, accountants, etc). For other data types, data security is controlled by measured document and/or folder level access rules. Data is accessible as follows:

- 1) Openly shared Google documents in edit-mode (some specific sub-folders of data type VII)
- 2) Openly shared Google documents in comment/suggest mode (some specific sub-folders of data type VII)
- 3) Specific-accounts-only - accessible Google documents (the RDA TIGER Google folder tree)

⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12568753>

⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17762711>

- 4) SharePoint documents (only accessible with SharePoint accounts internal to RDA Association) (data types I, III, IV, VI)
- 5) B2DROP documents (only accessible to specific persons controlled by WP6) - discontinued in 2025.

The RDA TIGER personnel are instructed on the correct security level used for different documents based on their need.

Working documents in Google folder structure are backed-up and versioned using integrated Google tools. SharePoint is regularly and automatically backed-up, and automatic versioning is available. WP4 creates back-ups of the RDA Knowledge Base in the DANS/KNAW Vault long-term preservation facility.

5. Ethics

The RDA TIGER considers the ethical aspects of the recorded data.

- Many datasets of the RDA TIGER, particularly connected to the WG work, included some level of personal information, particularly on the membership of the WG members. In most cases, the WG members volunteer this information themselves when signing attendance sheets. Although the membership in the RDA groups is public knowledge due to the RDA membership policies, this information is considered protected by the GDPR, and the retention of such information was controlled by WP1. The data protection statements and clear documentation on the usage of the data is provided to the WG members as per normal RDA policy. Data controller for the RDA Website published data is RDA Secretariat (based in the UK); the European Commission recognizes the adequacy of data protection measures in the UK.¹⁰
- To the extent to which RDA members are also authors of formal RDA outputs, such information is included in bibliographic metadata in Zenodo and in the RDA Knowledge Base, and are generally considered to be publicly available for purposes of findability and citation. The Knowledge Base has a dedicated privacy statement.
- Other data with more important ethical concerns, such as information on RDA TIGER applications, and particularly the reviewers' identity and review scores were controlled by WP6. This information will be destroyed after the GA mandated 5-year recording keeping requirement lapses.

¹⁰

https://commission.europa.eu/law/law-topic/data-protection/international-dimension-data-protection/adequacy-decisions_en

6. Other issues

6.1. Exploitation of the RDA TIGER and WG outputs

Although the exploitation plan of RDA TIGER is presented in D4.2, there is also a need to consider the result exploitation from the perspective of the datasets produced. The RDA TIGER concentrates the exploitation of the data products to the following key channels:

- 1) Service descriptions of the RDA TIGER services, including their user feedback and quality control aspects (without any personal data). These are intended to have long term storage in the RDA website, with additional archiving in the Zenodo repository. However, it is also important to note, that these outputs are then widely distributed and communicated to the RDA regional nodes and other RDA member organisations. Their metadata are also included in the RDA Knowledge Base.
- 2) The exploitation and user-based enrichment of the RDA Landscape data in the RDA Knowledge Base, and connecting the database with other landscape-creating studies, such as e.g. EOSC FOCUS.

Ensuring exploitation of these outputs was an additional long term target of the data management activities of the project.

